

THE IMPORTANCE OF AN INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT SYSTEM IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article deals with the issues of increasing the educational efficiency of primary and secondary school students and participation in evaluation studies at the international level, which are important for educational institutions.

Keywords: PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, TALIS, EGRA, EGMA, IHTT, international assessment program, math literacy, reading literacy, international requirements.

ВАЖНОСТЬ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ОЦЕНИВАНИЯ В НАЧАЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются важные для общеобразовательных учреждений вопросы повышения образовательной эффективности учащихся начальных и старших классов и участия в оценочных исследованиях на международном уровне.

Ключевые слова: PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, TALIS, EGRA, EGMA, IHTT, международная программа оценивания, математическая грамотность, грамотность чтения, международные требования.

BOSHLANG’ICH TA’LIMDA XALQARO BAHOLASH TIZIMINING AHAMIYATI

Annotatsiya: Maqolada umumiy o’rta ta’lim muassasalari boshlang’ich va yuqori sinf o’quvchilarining ta’lim samaradorligini oshirish va xalqaro darajada baholash tadqiqotlarida ishtirok etishi uchun muhim masalalar haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, TALIS, EGRA, EGMA, IHTT, xalqaro baholash dasturi, matematik savodxonlik, o’qish savodxonligi, xalqaro talablar.

Enter. More than a hundred countries in the world participate in international assessment studies such as PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, TALIS, EGRA and EGMA in order to objectively evaluate the quality of education implemented in their country. In particular, Uzbekistan is expected to participate in PISA and other international assessment studies for the first time. In the middle of the 21st century, the countries

of the world created the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (ECOD) in order to develop international economic relations. IHTT, which started its work in 1961, has been solving various problems that have arisen in the financial sector over the past period. Especially at the beginning of the new century, PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) was developed on the basis of this organization in order to develop general secondary education, which is the main link of world education. The reason for the economic organization to turn to the education sector is that the personnel for any field grows in schools and ordinary classrooms. In this sense, such a huge structure as IHTT was forced to make a ranking of how much money countries spend on the education system and how effective they are. Today, the international assessment program is in place to study, analyze, compare and set goals for future development of educational indicators in different countries of the world.

Literature review. Our original literature is called "Evaluation of reading literacy of elementary school students in international studies". This book was developed as a methodical guide for primary school teachers, methodologists and specialists in the field. It contains samples of texts on various topics to assess the reading literacy of primary school students. It is necessary for the students to read the text and answer the relevant questions. It can be used by teachers of mathematics, methodologists and experts in the field as a methodical guide. This book contains mathematical problems, their solutions and stages of logical thinking. The study guide on the assessment of students' reading literacy in international studies serves as a methodical guide for teachers of the native language and literature, and specialists in the field.

Research methodology. Our country has reached a period of rapid development on the path of innovative development. Comprehensive support for the creative ideas and creativity of young people, formation of their knowledge, skills and qualifications, as well as advanced foreign experiences, international standards and requirements. It is important to improve the evaluation system based on this, to study international experiences, to conduct a comprehensive comparative analysis of the existing system, to closely cooperate with relevant international and foreign organizations and scientific research institutions. According to him, international education experts have developed a universal test system to determine the level of students' mastery of subjects. In addition, the creators of the program also check the ability of students to apply their knowledge in practice. It was planned that the 4th grade students of our country will participate for the first time in the PIRLS international assessment program, which will be held in 2021, among about 70 countries. , was conducted in 2016, and 2021 is the fifth periodicity of the study. The PIRLS program, which is held every five years, evaluates the reading comprehension

skills of 4th grade students at an international level. This program is aimed at complementing the TIMSS program, which assesses the knowledge level of 4th grade students in mathematics and science. lib, the TIMSS and PIRLS International Center at Boston College is administered in close cooperation with the IEA offices in Hamburg and Amsterdam. is carried out by transfer. Also, surveys of school principals, teachers, students, and even parents are conducted to collect valuable information on factors affecting the quality of education.

The PIRLS international study provides an international comparison of information on the level of development of reading comprehension skills of primary school students, which can serve public policy in the field of education to improve reading and teaching. is a major international assessment program that provides analysis. Currently, according to PIRLS definition, reading literacy is the understanding and use of written language forms that are required by society and valued by humans, as well as the ability to create meaning from texts in various forms is also an ability. Within the framework of research, the main focus is on demonstrating understanding and how to apply the acquired information to new projects and situations. The student is an active participant in this process, creating meaning, text observes and consciously chooses effective reading strategies. Each type of text follows typical patterns and rules to help the reader interpret the text. Any text can have different forms. These include traditional books, magazines, documents and newspapers, as well as written forms in digital form. Focuses on "acquiring artistic experience", "getting information and using it". In turn, each of these goals integrates four broad comprehension processes.

*Preparation of primary school students for TIMSS international assessment program if organized effectively;

*Preparation of primary school students for TIMSS international assessment program if methods and tools are activated;

*The teacher works creatively in the educational process, mathematics and real life examples and logical concepts are appropriate in the lessons of natural science if used, students' educational activity will be effective

Analysis and results. Depending on the complexity of the texts in the study, on average 500-800 words, 400-500 for countries with low reading literacy, and about 1000 words in PIRLS. Content of the text Suitable for students aged 9-10, away from topics that are very specific to some cultures, as well as interesting and not very familiar to the student. The levels of reading literacy in the PIRLS study are described as follows:

Highest level (625 points and above) – Students can absorb a text as a whole while also understanding its individual parts in relation to each other. Can draw on the text to support his/her opinion when explaining the author's idea.

High level (550 points) - Students understand the important messages of the text, make their own conclusions based on the text, can evaluate both the content and form of the text, can pay attention to some of its linguistic features.

Intermediate level (475 points) – Students can find information from the text, draw their own conclusions based on the text using some features of text form and language.

Lower Level (400 points) – Students extract a clear message from a text that is easy to limit.

In the study, how well do elementary school graduates of Uzbekistan study compared to their peers in other countries? What is the reading literacy of Uzbekistan's students? Is reading a hobby for 4th graders? How does the family contribute to the development of literacy? How is the process of teaching reading organized in our country today? Is the process of teaching reading in Uzbekistan unique compared to other countries, and if so, how is it manifested? Are the methods used by our primary school teachers different from the methods used by teachers in other countries? In addition, in order to study and analyze the factors affecting the quality of education, questionnaire surveys will be conducted. Including information about the participant through the student questionnaire, educational resources in the family, attitudes towards the school, the teacher, the academic subject, the attitude between the students, the study of the academic subjects information about self-assessment, extracurricular activities is collected. The teacher questionnaire includes information about teachers, school equipment, safety, school environment, teaching methods, and professional development. In the parents' questionnaire, information about parents, educational resources in the family, preparation of their child for school, skills and qualifications before admission to school, parents' attitude to school and education are studied.

The school's capacity, location, equipment, educational resources, organization of the educational process at the school, school environment are studied and analyzed through the questionnaire of the school administration. According to the 2016 study, out of 50 countries, Russia, Singapore, Hong Kong, Ireland and Finland had the highest scores, while Russian and Singaporean students scored the highest in reading and comprehension. showed the results. Russian primary school students also led the world in this criterion.

Conclusion/Recommendations. The high results of reading literacy in these countries are related to the following factors: the availability of books and digital devices in the home, intelligent parents and their love for books, the fact that the child learned to read and write before school, and The participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the PIRLS research serves to increase the quality of education, strengthen the country's reputation at the international level, and bring the students'

knowledge to the level of international requirements. In short, by participating in TIMSS and other international studies, Uzbekistan will have the opportunity to apply the experiences of developed countries in the educational system of Uzbekistan and compare its results with the results of other countries. Continuous participation in the study every four years allows to increase the effectiveness of the education system of our country on a global scale.

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